
1 Spectroscopic Analyses of Photoconversion in Phytochromes

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11 Abstract

12 Phytochrome photoreceptors integrate red and far-red light to inform vital adaptations of
13 physiology, development, and lifestyle in manifold plants, bacteria, and fungi. Once covalently
14 assembled with bilin chromophores, phytochromes traverse their metastable Pr and Pfr states
15 depending on light quality and intensity. This chapter provides protocols for the analyses of
16 phytochromes by absorption spectroscopy to determine their molar extinction coefficients; their
17 photostationary state assumed under constant illumination; and their quantum yields for the light-
18 driven Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr interconversion. Knowledge of these parameters pertains to the natural role of
19 phytochromes and their deployment in optogenetics and biotechnology.

20 Keywords

21 bilin; chromophore; optogenetics; photobiology; phytochrome; photoreceptor; quantum yield;
22 spectroscopy

23 1. Introduction

24 In nature, organisms must perceive environmental cues to adapt to changing living conditions. Light
25 is one of the most important stimuli, and organisms have evolved numerous sensory photoreceptors
26 to react to it. As one major class, phytochromes (Phy) [1, 2] recur in plants, algae, fungi, and bacteria
27 where they underlie diverse physiological responses to red and far-red light, e.g., morphogenesis
28 [3], germination [4], and photoprotection [5]. As different as these processes and the underlying
29 photoreceptors are, the so-called photosensory core module (PCM), responsible for light absorption,
30 is conserved throughout the Phy family. A bilin chromophore nestles within the PCM and is
31 covalently attached to a cysteine residue, thereby granting sensitivity to red and far-red light [1, 2].
32 Plant Phys use phytochromobilin (PΦB) as their natural chromophore but can be functionally
33 reconstituted with the cyanobacterial phycocyanobilin (PCB) [6, 7]. By contrast, bacterial Phys
34 incorporate biliverdin (BV) [5, 8], a more oxidized bilin that serves as the precursor to both PΦB and
35 PCB biosynthesis. Bilins exhibit characteristic absorbance bands within the visible portion of the
36 electromagnetic spectrum, namely the Q band in the red/far-red region [9] and the Soret band in
37 the blue region [10]. Not least owing to differing extents of the conjugated π electron systems in the
38 respective bilins, bacterial Phys display a bathochromic shift by around 50 nm of their Q-band
39 absorbance compared to plant Phys [1, 2, 11]. That notwithstanding, the principal photochemistry
40 playing out upon light absorption is conserved across the Phy superfamily. Phys can adopt two
41 metastable states, called Pr and Pfr (pigment red-absorbing and pigment far-red absorbing [12]),
42 which differ in the isomerization of the C15=C16 double bond of the bilin [1, 2]. In the red-light-
43 absorbing Pr state, the chromophore adopts its 15Z isomer, and in the far-red-light-absorbing Pfr
44 state it is the 15E configuration. In plant and prototypical bacterial Phys, the Pr state prevails in
45 darkness, whereas a group of bacterial Phys adopt the Pfr state in darkness and are denoted as
46 bathyphytochromes. Red and far-red light promotes the photoconversion in the Pr→Pfr and Pfr→Pr

47 directions, respectively. The underlying transition rates between the two states depend on the
48 applied light quality and intensity [13], as well as on the bilin absorption cross section at the
49 excitation wavelength multiplied by the quantum yield (Note 1) for photoconversion. Returned to
50 darkness, phytochromes generally revert to their original dark-adapted state in a thermal reaction
51 denoted dark recovery that can be protracted and last up to several days.

52 This chapter treats the spectroscopic analyses of absorbance and $\text{Pr} \rightleftharpoons \text{Pfr}$ photoconversion in
53 plant and bacterial phytochromes. With the PCMs of *Arabidopsis thaliana* phytochrome B (*AtPhyB*)
54 [14], the prototypical Phy from *Deinococcus maricopensis* (*DmPCM*) [15, 16], and the
55 bathyphytochrome from *Agrobacterium vitis* (*AvPCM*) [15, 17, 18] as paradigms, we discuss in turn
56 the calculation of molar extinction coefficients for Phy holoproteins (section 3.1); the quantification
57 of the Pr:Pfr ratio assumed at photostationary state under constant red light (section 3.2); and the
58 determination of quantum yields for photoconversion between the Pr and Pfr states (section 3.3).
59 Collectively, the methods collated in this chapter are suited for characterizing photochemical traits
60 in Phys that equally pertain to their natural roles and their applications for biotechnology and
61 optogenetics [6, 16, 19, 20].

62 2. Materials

- 63 1. Purified proteins: *AtPhyB* [7, 14], *DmPCM* [15, 16], and *AvPCM* [15, 18], stored at -80°C
- 64 2. Native buffer: 50 mM Tris-HCl, 20 mM NaCl, pH 8.0. This buffer is used herein, but other
65 buffers can be used as demanded by the protein of interest.
- 66 3. Denaturing buffer: 50 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl, 6 M guanidine hydrochloride, pH 8.0. As
67 above, different buffers may be used as dictated by the specific protein under study.
- 68 4. UV/vis absorption spectrophotometer: e.g., Cary60 (Agilent Technologies), equipped with
69 Peltier temperature control

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- 70 5. Quartz glass microcuvette: 1 cm light path, 100 μ L volume
- 71 6. Quartz glass fluorescence microcuvette: 0.5 cm light path, 850 μ L volume
- 72 7. Light-emitting diodes (LED): e.g., the following, all obtained from Roithner Lasertechnik: (650
73 \pm 10) nm (no. H2A1-H650); (658 \pm 10) nm (no. JET-660-12); (733 \pm 12) nm (no. JET-730-10);
74 (757 \pm 12) nm (no. SMB1N-760D-02); and (800 \pm 18) nm (no. JET-800-10) (Note 2)
- 75 8. 3D-printed adapters for Cary60 spectrophotometer: available from
76 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14752680>
- 77 9. Power meter: e.g., Newport model 842-PE equipped with a 918D-UV-OD3 silicon detector

78 **3. Methods**

79 **3.1 Determination of Phytochrome Extinction Coefficients**

80 The concentration determination of phytochromes and, consequently, their use in any functional *in*
81 *vitro* assays hinge on accurate molar extinction coefficients for the bilin-bound holoproteins. Owing
82 to its strong absorbance, the bilin Q band is well suited for pertinent absorption-spectroscopic
83 analyses, with the caveat that its extinction coefficient strongly depends on the surrounding protein
84 scaffold and protonation status. To address this challenge, two separate UV/vis absorbance spectra
85 are recorded at the same phytochrome concentration, but once in native and once in denaturing
86 buffer. As within the denatured state, the extinction coefficients of the protein-bound bilins are to
87 first approximation independent of the protein context, the bilin absorbance properties within the
88 native holo-phytochrome can be inferred by comparison of the two spectra. Using this approach, we
89 routinely determine molar extinction coefficients at the isosbestic point for the Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr transition
90 which affords the advantage that concentrations can be calculated irrespective of the illumination
91 status of the phytochrome sample.

- 92 1. All experiments should be performed under dim green safe light to minimize inadvertent
93 photoactivation of the phytochrome samples.
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- 94 2. Equilibrate the UV/vis absorption spectrophotometer at a temperature of 22°C and record a
95 blank spectrum for the native buffer.
- 96 3. Dilute phytochromes into native buffer (Note 3) and load 120 μL into the quartz microcuvette
97 with an optical path length of 1 cm. Record absorbance spectra in darkness and after
98 saturating illumination with LEDs emitting red and far-red light, respectively. For plant
99 phytochromes, 660-nm and 730-nm LEDs can for instance be used to drive the Pr \rightarrow Pfr and
100 Pfr \rightarrow Pr transitions, respectively. In the case of bacterial phytochromes, a far-red LED emitting
101 around 800 nm can be deployed instead of the 730-nm LED.
- 102 4. Record a blank spectrum for the denaturing buffer. Dilute phytochromes into the denatured
103 buffer by the same factor as above for the native buffer (Note 4). Incubate for at least 5
104 minutes to allow for denaturation. Record spectra as described above.
- 105 5. As required, correct all spectra for potential baseline shifts by considering the absorbance
106 around 800 nm (for plant Phys) or around 900 nm (for bacterial Phys). Plot the spectra, e.g.,
107 with the freely available Fit-o-mat software [21] (Figure 1).
- 108 6. Calculate the chromophore concentration in the Phy proteins based on the denatured
109 spectra and the molar extinction coefficients of the protein-bound bilins. For P Φ B, PCB, and
110 BV, the relevant extinction coefficients within the Soret band are 36,000 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 380 nm
111 [22], 34,700 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 352 nm [22], and 39,900 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 388 nm [23], respectively.
- 112 7. With the knowledge of the bilin concentration, calculate the molar extinction coefficients of
113 the native holoproteins at the isosbestic point (or, at other desired wavelengths) via the Beer-
114 Lambert law [24, 25] (Note 5, Table 1).

115 3.2 Determination of the Pr:Pfr Ratio at Photostationary State

116 Due to the considerable overlap between the Pr and Pfr action spectra, illumination with red light
117 generally populates a Pr:Pfr mixture rather than the pure Pfr state (Figure 1). By contrast, exposure

118 to far-red light can in principle drive the phytochrome to its Pr state essentially in entirety. Not least
119 for quantitative analyses, e.g., Yi *et al.* [13], it is often imperative to know the precise Pr and Pfr
120 proportions assumed at photostationary state under red light. To this end, Butler *et al.* [26]
121 developed a formalism to calculate the Pr:Pfr ratio at the photostationary state and hence also the
122 pure Pfr absorbance spectrum. We describe in the following the application of the Butler method to
123 the *AtPhyB* and *DmPCM* samples as representatives for plant and bacterial phytochromes.

- 124 1. All experiments should be performed under dim green safe light to minimize inadvertent
125 photoactivation of the phytochrome samples.
- 126 2. Equilibrate the UV/vis absorption spectrophotometer at a temperature of 22°C and record a
127 blank spectrum for the native buffer.
- 128 3. Dilute the phytochrome protein in its dark-adapted state into native buffer (Note 3) and load
129 120 µL into the quartz microcuvette with an optical length of 1 cm. Record absorbance
130 spectra in darkness and after saturating exposure to red (emission around 650 to 660 nm)
131 and far-red LEDs (emission around 730 nm for plant Phys, and around 800 nm for bacterial
132 ones), respectively.
- 133 4. Populate the Pr state by exposing the sample to saturating far-red light.
- 134 5. Expose the Pr-state sample to red light at an intensity of around 1 mW cm⁻² while tracking
135 the resultant Pr→Pfr conversion kinetics by recording absorbance at 725 nm (*AtPhyB*) or 760
136 nm (*DmPCM*) (Figure 2, Note 6).
- 137 6. Partially populate the Pfr state by exposing the sample to saturating red light.
- 138 7. Expose sample to far-red light at an intensity of around 1-2 mW cm⁻² and track the resultant
139 Pfr→Pr conversion kinetics by recording absorbance at 725 nm (*AtPhyB*) or 760 nm (*DmPCM*)
140 (Figure 2).
- 141 8. Evaluate the Pr⇌Pfr photoconversion kinetics [26] by fitting the time-resolved absorbance
142 data to a single-exponential function eq. (1), e.g., using the Fit-o-mat software [21]:

$$A(t) = A_0 + A_1 \times \exp(-k_i \times t) \quad (1)$$

143 where A_0 is the final absorbance reading; $A_0 + A_1$ is the initial absorbance value; and k_i
 144 represents the rate constant of the $\text{Pr} \rightleftharpoons \text{Pfr}$ photoconversion kinetics for a given illumination
 145 regime. For the $\text{Pr} \rightarrow \text{Pfr}$ and $\text{Pfr} \rightarrow \text{Pr}$ conversion kinetics, we denote the underlying rate
 146 constants as k_p and k_q , respectively (Figure 2).

147 9. Calculate the mole fractions of P_R and P_{FR} at red-light induced photostationary state
 148 according to eq. (2, 3) adapted from Butler *et al.* [26]:

$$\frac{C_R}{C_{FR}} = \frac{E_{FR}}{E_R} \times \frac{A_{light}^{FR}}{A_{dark}^R} \times \frac{k_p}{k_q} \quad (2)$$

$$P_R = 1 - P_{FR} = \frac{1}{1 + C_R/C_{FR}} \times \frac{A_{light}^R}{A_{dark}^R} \quad (3)$$

149 where C_R and C_{FR} are the photoconversion amplitudes for red and far-red light with photon
 150 fluxes of E_R and E_{FR} , respectively (Note 7). A_{dark}^R and A_{light}^R refer to the absorbance within
 151 the dark-adapted and the red-light-induced photostationary states at the emission maximum
 152 of the red-light source. (Note that the dark-adapted Pr spectrum can be obtained upon
 153 saturating application of far-red light.) Likewise, A_{light}^{FR} denotes the absorbance of the
 154 photostationary state at the peak wavelength of the far-red-light source.

155 10. Calculate the pure Pfr spectrum A_{Pfr} according to eq. (4):

$$A_{Pfr}(\lambda) = \frac{A_{light}(\lambda) - A_{dark}(\lambda) \times P_R}{P_{FR}} \quad (4)$$

156 where A_{dark} and A_{light} are the absorbance spectra after saturating exposure to far-red and red
 157 light; and P_R and P_{FR} denote the Pr and Pfr mole fractions at photostationary state
 158 determined above (Figure 1, Table 1).

159 11. The principal approach extends to bathyphytochromes, but the analyses are complicated by
 160 the comparatively fast $\text{Pr} \rightarrow \text{Pfr}$ dark recovery which may hinder accurate determination of

161 the Pfr \rightleftharpoons Pr photoconversion kinetics. Rather, an alternative and simpler approach is feasible
162 as the pure Pr-state and Pfr-state spectra can be directly recorded and need not be
163 calculated. That is because bathyphytochromes adopt their Pfr state in darkness, and far-red
164 light can prompt the complete photoconversion to the Pr state. With the knowledge of the
165 pure states, Pr:Pfr mixtures assumed at photostationary state can be analysed in terms of a
166 linear combination of the pure Pr and Pfr spectra.

167 3.3 Determination of Photoconversion Quantum Yields

168 This section regards the Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr interconversion efficiency and the associated photoconversion
169 quantum yields (Φ_i). As described in Yi *et al.* [14] (Note 8) and similar to Stadler *et al.* [27], the
170 quantum yield Φ_p for the Pr \rightarrow Pfr photoconversion of prototypical phytochromes like *AtPhyB* and
171 *DmPCM* can be inferred from absorption spectroscopy (Note 9). Likewise, the quantum yield Φ_q for
172 the Pfr \rightarrow Pr photoconversion can be determined for bathyphytochromes, e.g., *AvPCM*.

- 173 1. All experiments should be performed under dim green safe light to minimize inadvertent
174 photoactivation of the phytochrome samples.
- 175 2. Equip UV/vis spectrophotometer with a cuvette holder for the fluorescence microcuvette
176 with 0.5 cm optical path length, e.g., using the template file for a 3D-printed adapter for the
177 Cary60 instrument, as supplied in the Materials section (Note 10).
- 178 3. Equilibrate the UV/vis absorption spectrophotometer at ambient temperature and record a
179 blank spectrum for the native buffer.
- 180 4. Dilute the dark-adapted phytochrome sample into native buffer (Note 1) and load 400 μ L
181 into the 0.5-cm fluorescence cuvette. Record absorbance spectra after saturating exposure
182 to red (emission around 650 to 660 nm) and far-red LEDs (emission around 730 nm for plant
183 Phys, and around 800 nm for bacterial ones), respectively.

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- 184 5. Calculate the holoprotein concentration c_0 using the Beer-Lambert law [25, 26] with the
185 extinction coefficients determined in section 3.1 (Table 1).
- 186 6. Remove the cuvette and position an actinic light source in front of the instrument
187 perpendicular to the UV/vis detection beam of the spectrophotometer (Figure 3). To drive
188 the Pr→Pfr transition of the prototypical *AtPhyB* and *DmPCM*, LEDs emitting around 650 to
189 660 nm are used. In the case of the bathyphytochrome *AvPCM*, a 760-nm LED is employed
190 to promote the Pfr→Pr photoconversion. Adjust the light intensity P_0 of the actinic LED to
191 around 0.5 mW cm⁻² using a lamp power meter.
- 192 7. Switch off the actinic LED and place the cuvette back into the instrument. Convert the sample
193 to its dark-adapted state. To this end, *AtPhyB* and *DmPCM* are illuminated with LEDs emitting
194 around 730 nm and 800 nm, respectively, to drive the Pfr→Pr photoconversion. Owing to its
195 fast dark recovery [17, 18], the *AvPCM* can be incubated inside the spectrophotometer for
196 around 5 minutes to passively return to its dark-adapted Pfr state.
- 197 8. Switch on the actinic light and follow the Pr→Pfr photoconversion (for *AtPhyB* and *DmPCM*)
198 or the Pfr→Pr photoconversion (for *AvPCM*), respectively, by tracking the absorbance at the
199 peak wavelength λ of the actinic light source (Note 9, Figure 4).
- 200 9. Evaluate the resultant absorbance kinetics by fitting to a single-exponential function eq. (1),
201 e.g., using the Fit-o-mat software [21], and thereby determine the photoconversion rate
202 constant k_i (Figure 4).
- 203 10. Calculate the photoconversion quantum yield Φ_i according to eq. (5) (Table 1):

$$\Phi_i = \frac{k_i \times c_0 \times w \times h \times c \times N_A}{\lambda \times P_0 \times (1 - 10^{-A_0})} \quad (5)$$

204 where k_i is the photoconversion rate constant; c_0 is the sample concentration inside the
205 cuvette; w is the cuvette width; λ is the peak wavelength of the actinic LED source; h is
206 Planck's constant (6.63×10^{-34} J s); c denotes the speed of light (3×10^8 m s⁻¹); N_A is Avogadro's

207 constant ($6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$); P_0 denotes the applied light intensity (in $\text{J m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$); and A_0 is the
208 initial absorbance at wavelength λ of the dark-adapted sample prior to illumination. For more
209 details see Note 8 and Yi *et al.* [13].

210 11. In the case of prototypical phytochromes, knowledge of the Pr \rightarrow Pfr photoconversion
211 quantum yield Φ_p enables the calculation of the quantum yield Φ_q for the reverse Pfr \rightarrow Pr
212 photoconversion at the same excitation wavelength [26] (Note 11). The pure Pr and Pfr
213 spectra determined in section 3.2 yield the absorbance values for the two states, A_{Pr} and A_{Pfr} ,
214 at a given excitation wavelength λ . Then, the quotient $(1 - 10^{-A_{Pr}})/(1 - 10^{-A_{Pfr}})$ is proportional
215 to the number of photons absorbed by the Pr vs. the Pfr state. Upon saturating illumination
216 at the excitation wavelength λ , a photostationary state with Pr and Pfr proportions of P_R and
217 P_{FR} is assumed (see section 3.2). The ratio of the quantum yields Φ_p and Φ_q for the
218 bidirectional Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr interconversion is then just given by eq. (6):

$$\Phi_q/\Phi_p = P_R/P_{FR} \times (1 - 10^{-A_{Pr}})/(1 - 10^{-A_{Pfr}}) \quad (6)$$

219 Similarly, for bathyphytochromes Φ_p can be derived from the experimentally determined
220 value of Φ_q .

221 4. Notes

- 222 1. The quantum yield denotes the number of defined events, here Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr photoconversion,
223 occurring per photon absorbed.
- 224 2. Other lamp, LED, or laser light sources emitting at similar wavelengths and with sufficient
225 output power can be used as well. Generally, lasers bring the advantage of narrower emission
226 spectra compared to LEDs. As required, LED and lamp emission spectra can be narrowed by
227 using band-pass interference filters.
- 228 3. Adjust concentration such that the peak absorbance within the Q band ranges between 0.1
229 and 0.2.

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- 230 4. It is imperative that the dilution into the native and denaturing buffers be prepared in the
 231 same manner, i.e., using a joint dilution factor. Any inaccuracy in preparing the dilutions will
 232 directly factor into the subsequent analyses. Ideally, repeat the experiment several times and
 233 average the results.
- 234 5. The isosbestic point within the Q band is determined for the native samples and refers to the
 235 intersection of the absorbance traces obtained upon illumination with red and far-red light.
 236 Note that this approach implicitly assumes a two-state transition between the Pr and Pfr
 237 forms of the phytochrome. If additional states are populated throughout the photocycle,
 238 isosbestic points where the absorbance spectra of all these states would intersect may not
 239 exist.
- 240 6. The subsequent analyses require a stable LED output. Therefore, turn on the LEDs 30 min
 241 before measurement to reduce intensity fluctuations.
- 242 7. Light intensities are measured with a power meter and assumed to be in units $W \times cm^{-2}$. For
 243 use in eq. (2), the intensity can be converted into units of photons $\times m^{-2} \times s^{-1}$ with eq. (13):

$$E_{\lambda} = \frac{I_{\lambda} \times \lambda}{h \times c \times N_A} \quad (13)$$

244 where E_{λ} is photon flux per unit time and area; I_{λ} the measured light intensity per area at the
 245 excitation wavelength λ ; h Planck's constant; N_A Avogadro's constant; and c the speed of light.

- 246 8. The quantum yield Φ_i can be calculated as described [14] by correlating the absorbed light
 247 power per unit time with the initial drop in the Pr state population (or, Pfr for AvPCM).
 248 According to the Beer-Lambert law [24, 25], the light intensity $d\Delta P/dt$ absorbed by the
 249 sample per unit time and area amounts to:

$$d\Delta P/dt = P_0 \times (1 - 10^{-A_{\lambda}(t)}) \quad (7)$$

250 where $A_\lambda(t)$ denotes the sample absorbance at the peak wavelength λ of the actinic light.
 251 Converting the light intensity to photon flux yields the number of absorbed photons per unit
 252 time and area, dn'/dt :

$$dn'/dt = d\Delta P/dt \times \lambda \times (h \times c \times N_A)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

253 where h is the Planck constant; c the speed of light; and N_A Avogadro's number. Considering
 254 the cross-sectional area of the cuvette (A), one obtains the number of absorbed photons
 255 within the cuvette per unit of time:

$$dn/dt = A \times dn'/dt = A \times d\Delta P/dt \times \lambda \times (h \times c \times N_A)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

256 The absorbance kinetics provide the decrease of Phy concentration c_i in the Pr state (for
 257 AtPhyB and DmPCM) or the Pfr state (for AvPCM) per unit time:

$$dc_i/dt = -k_i \times c_i(t) \quad (10)$$

258 Multiplication by the reaction volume V , yields the decrease in the number of Pr-state (for
 259 AtPhyB and DmPCM) or Pfr-state (for AvPCM) molecules over time:

$$dn_i/dt = dc_i/dt \times V = -k_i \times c_i(t) \times A \times w \quad (11)$$

260 where w is the width of the cuvette (Figure 3).

261 Accordingly, the quantum yield Φ_i corresponds to the ratio of reacting molecules per unit
 262 time, $-dn_i/dt$, over the number of absorbed photons per time, dn/dt :

$$\Phi_i = \frac{-dn_i/dt}{dn/dt} = k_i \times c_i(t) \times \frac{w}{\lambda \times (h \times c \times N_A)^{-1} \times P_0 \times (1 - 10^{-A_\lambda(t)})} \quad (12)$$

263 At the beginning of the experiment, i.e., $t \rightarrow 0$, the quantum yield Φ_i can be thus calculated
 264 from the measurable quantities k_i , c_0 , P_0 , and A_0 as described in eq. (5).

265 9. The photoconversion quantum yield Φ_i is determined for a specific temperature T and
 266 excitation wavelength λ . The absorption of light of other wavelengths may drive different
 267 electronic and vibronic transitions within the bilin, and hence the resultant quantum yield

268 for photoconversion may differ in principle. However, as further elaborated in Note 11,
269 evidence exists that the photoconversion quantum yield remains largely invariant across the
270 entire Q band at least.

271 10. A cuvette with 0.5 cm path length is chosen to lower sample consumption and to reduce the
272 inner-filter effect. Other cuvettes (and, if required, sample adapters) may be used provided
273 that the actinic light illuminates the entire sample surface A and passes through the cuvette
274 without being reflected back (Figure 3).

275 11. Apart from it being straight-forward, the calculation of the quantum yield for the reverse
276 photoconversion is mandated by at least two principal considerations. First, owing to the
277 substantial spectral overlap between the Pr and Pfr states (see Fig. 1), many light qualities,
278 e.g., red light, will drive both the Pr \rightarrow Pfr and the Pfr \rightarrow Pr photoconversion. The flux in either
279 direction is proportional to the respective molar extinction coefficients, i.e., for the Pr and
280 Pfr states, at the excitation wavelength multiplied by the quantum yields Φ_p and Φ_q ,
281 respectively. In turn, these quantities govern the photostationary state and the speed of
282 bidirectional Pr \rightleftharpoons Pfr interconversion under constant illumination. As we recently elucidated
283 for plant phytochromes [13], knowledge of these parameters is of paramount importance
284 when assessing and rationalizing downstream signaling responses. Second, to the extent the
285 action spectra of phytochromes have been determined, they often closely resemble their
286 absorbance spectra, at least within the Q band. This immediately argues for largely uniform
287 photoconversion quantum yields across the entire Q band, as indeed experimentally borne
288 out for plant phytochromes [26]. Therefore, it is expected that the determination of Φ_p and
289 Φ_q at a discrete wavelength provides a good estimator for other wavelengths within the Q
290 band, too.

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362

364 **Figure 1**

365 Spectroscopic analyses of phytochromes. **(a)** UV/vis absorbance spectra of phytochromobilin (PΦB)-
 366 bound photosensory core module (PCM) of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* phytochrome B (AtPhyB) in its
 367 Pr state (purple) after far-red light illumination and in the mixed Pr/Pfr state (red) following red-
 368 light illumination. The dashed line represents the calculated absorbance spectrum for the pure Pfr
 369 state as described in section 3.2. **(b)** As in (a) but for the biliverdin (BV)-bound PCM from the *Dein-*
 370 *ococcus maricopenis* phytochrome (*DmPCM*). **(c)** As in (a) but for the BV-bound PCM of the *Agro-*
 371 *bacterium vitis* phytochrome (*AvPCM*) in its dark-adapted Pfr state (black), in its Pr state (purple)
 372 after far-red light illumination, and in the mixed Pr/Pfr state (red) under red light. **(d)** Absorbance
 373 spectra of the denatured AtPhyB (dark green), *DmPCM* (light green), and *AvPCM* (blue) samples
 374 from panels (a-c) normalized to their Soret absorbance maxima.

376 **Figure 2**

377

378 Analyses of the $\text{Pr} \rightleftharpoons \text{Pfr}$ photoconversion kinetics in phytochrome photosensory core modules (PCM)379 to determine the Pr:Pfr ratio adopted under red light according to Butler [26]. **(a)** Pr→Pfr (red) and

380 Pfr→Pr photoconversion kinetics (purple) for the phytochromobilin (PΦB)-bound PCM of

381 *Arabidopsis thaliana* phytochrome B (AtPhyB) under red (660 nm, 1 mW cm^{-2}) and far-red-light (730382 nm, 2 mW cm^{-2}), respectively. The dashed vertical line marks the onset of irradiation, and the383 ensuing kinetics were monitored by the absorbance at 725 nm. The values for k_p and k_q in the graph384 represent mean \pm s.d. of three technical replicates. **(b)** As for (a) but for the biliverdin (BV)-bound385 PCM from the *Deinococcus maricopensis* phytochrome (*DmPCM*). The Pr→Pfr and Pfr→Pr386 transitions were driven by exposure to 650-nm (1 mW cm^{-2}) and 800-nm light (2.5 mW cm^{-2}),

387 respectively, and followed by the absorbance at 760 nm.

388 **Figure 3**

389

390 Experimental setup for the photoconversion quantum-yield measurements. **(a)** Schematic of the
391 experiment. Protein samples are loaded into a quartz fluorescence microcuvette of path length w
392 and are exposed to actinic light perpendicular to the probe beam of the UV/vis spectrophotometer
393 at a light power of P_0 (red arrow). The light intensity of the probe beam I_0 and the light intensity I
394 passing through the sample are indicated by black arrows. **(b)** (left) Photograph of the experimental
395 setup schematized in panel (a). (right) Setup for determination of the power P_0 of the actinic light
396 source using a lamp power meter.

398

399 Photoconversion kinetics of phytochrome photosensory core modules (PCM). **(a)** Pr→Pfr conversion400 kinetics of phytochromobilin (PΦB)-bound PCM of *Arabidopsis thaliana* phytochrome B (AtPhyB)401 during irradiation with 660-nm light (0.45 mW cm^{-2}) as monitored by the absorbance at 660 nm.402 The photoconversion rate constant stated in the graph refers to the mean \pm s.d. of three technical403 replicates. **(b)** As in (a) but for the AtPhyB PCM bound to phycocyanobilin (PCB). **(c)** As in (a) but for404 the biliverdin (BV)-bound PCM from the *Deinococcus maricopensis* phytochrome (DmPCM) exposed405 to 650-nm light (0.5 mW cm^{-2}) and monitored at 650 nm. **(d)** Pfr→Pr conversion kinetics of the BV-406 bound PCM of the *Agrobacterium vitis* phytochrome (AvPCM) exposed to 757-nm light (0.5 mW cm^{-2})

407 as tracked by the absorbance at 757 nm.

408 **Table 1 – Collated parameters of the investigated phytochromes.**

Phytochrome	Bilin	Isosbestic point [nm]	Holoprotein extinction coefficient ^a [$M^{-1} cm^{-1}$]	Pr:Pfr ratio	Quantum Yield ^d		
						λ [nm]	Φ_i
<i>AtPhyB</i>	P Φ B	686	41,300	0.24:0.76 ^b	Pr→Pfr	658	0.20 ± 0.02
<i>AtPhyB</i>	PCB	674	48,200	0.27:0.73 ^b	Pr→Pfr	658	0.24 ± 0.01
<i>DmPCM</i>	BV	721	36,400	0.21:0.79 ^b	Pr→Pfr	650	0.23 ± 0.01
<i>AvPCM</i>	BV	710	38,900	0.21:0.79 ^c	Pfr→Pr	757	0.12 ± 0.01

409 ^a: The extinction coefficients are reported for the isosbestic points listed in the table, see section
 410 3.1.

411 ^b: Calculated according to Butler *et al.* [26], see section 3.2.

412 ^c: Determined as a linear combination of the near-pure Pr and Pfr spectra.

413 ^d: Determined as described in section 3.3.